

Historical Analysis of the Evolution of Primary Public Health Policies in India before and after Independence up to the 1990s

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ABSTRACT

The state uses its authority to organize, prioritize, carry out, and evaluate health activities even in alternative configurations. In order to identify issues with the present primary mental health care policy and programme, it is important to look into and analyze the historical, political, cultural, and other elements. The study is based on qualitative and quantitative data sources to identify elements of the healthcare and health profile of the Indian population, the approaches of health policies, the expansion of healthcare services in pre- and post-independence India, equity and disparities in healthcare indicators, and accessibility of care among various groups and sub-groups in the Indian society. The paper suggested that every country create a national health policy. In general, it was believed that India's high mortality and high fertility rates ranged between 40 and 40 per 1000 people.

Keywords: historical, evolution, public, health policy, pre-independence and post-independence.

Introduction

There are numerous aspects that influence people's overall health. Particularly in federal and socialist institutions, the state's role is crucial for achieving health standards at the community level. The state uses its authority to organize, prioritize, carry out, and evaluate health activities even in alternative configurations. This is done through policies, programmes, and laws. Every endeavor ought to be preceded by a policy, which is a tenet or directive meant to direct actions and produce reasonable results. The implementation of a policy takes the form of a procedure or protocol. A policy is a statement of intent. While senior executive officers in India design and implement protocols or processes, state or central governments in India often enact health policies. Indian traditional medicine has a rich history dating back to the pre-colonial era; however it would be beneficial and imperative to concentrate on the present public health system (prevalent in the colonial as well as post-colonial period). The western medical system was initially introduced to India by the colonial authority for its own purposes, and its effects were limited to a tiny segment of the population. The benefit of this health system was first for the families of European civil and military employees, but later, some urban-dwelling Indians were also given access to this medical care. India's first National Health Policy (NHP-1) was created in 1983 with the stated goal of achieving "Health for All by 2000 AD" through basic healthcare. But after ten years, the Indian government softened its stance and adopted the World Bank's recommendations, allowing the health sector and all other social sectors to become commercialized as part of the country's globalization strategy. Because the cost of healthcare is rising dramatically in the form of "out-of-pocket expenditure," accessibility disparities in healthcare are widening quickly since the advent of globalization. The majority of the population is pushed into poverty and debt by healthcare prices. The majority of Indians devote approximately two-thirds of their income to healthcare, with the remaining one-third going toward other expenses.

Review of Literature

To investigate and analyze the political, cultural, and other historical factors that have contributed to the DMHP's triumphs and failures since 1947 (the post-independence era), as doing so may reveal problems with the current primary mental health care policy and programme. In 2010–2011, oral history interviews and documentary sources with decision-makers, programme managers, and observers who had participated in the development of the NMHP and DMHP were done. The findings imply that the generally held belief that the DMHP has failed is not totally accurate, in that

significant obstacles to the plan's implementation rather than flaws with the plan itself have had an influence on mental health coverage in primary care. These obstacles have included political indifference, ineffective national, state, and district leadership, unavailable money, and incorrect¹.

In order to identify issues with the present primary mental health care policy and programme, it is important to look into and analyse the historical, political, cultural, and other elements that have influenced the DMHP's successes and failures since 1947 (the post-independence era). Oral history interviews and archival research were conducted with decision-makers, programme managers, and observers who had contributed to the creation of the NMHP and DMHP in 2010-2011. The results suggest that the widely held notion that the DMHP has failed is not entirely true, since severe implementation challenges rather than problems in the plan's design have affected the availability of mental health coverage in primary care. These challenges have included lack of funding, weak national, state, and district leadership, and political disinterest². Policies from many eras of the nation's history, including colonial subjugation, apartheid dispossession, and the post-apartheid period, can be traced as the origin of a dysfunctional health system and the collision of epidemics of infectious and non-communicable diseases in South Africa. In South Africa's difficult past, racial and gender discrimination, the migrant labour system, the dissolution of families, enormous income disparities, and terrible violence all had an unavoidable impact on health and health services. The health system encountered enormous difficulties after apartheid ended in 1994, many of which are still present today. Despite a significant increase in social grants, macroeconomic policies that encouraged growth rather than redistribution were a factor in the continuation of racial economic disparities³.

¹ Van Ginneken, N., Jain, S., Patel, V., & Berridge, V. (2014). The development of mental health services within primary care in India: learning from oral history. *International journal of mental health systems*, 8(1), 1-14.

² MALAKAR, N. (2020). Evaluating the evolution of health policy in India. *Science and Culture*.

³ Coovadia, H., Jewkes, R., Barron, P., Sanders, D., & McIntyre, D. (2009). The health and health system of South Africa: historical roots of current public health challenges. *The lancet*, 374(9692), 817-834.

Research Methodology

The study is based on qualitative and quantitative data sources to identify elements of the healthcare and health profile of the Indian population, the approaches of health policies, the expansion of healthcare services in pre- and post-independence India, equity and disparities in healthcare indicators, and accessibility of care among various groups and sub-groups in the Indian society.

Exploring Public Health Policies in Pre-Independence India

Prior to India's independence, a framework for public health policy and health planning already existed. In order to offer the country a free, state-organized health service, the "Health Survey and Development Committee," also known as the "Bhore Committee," published a thorough and exhaustive study on health planning in 1946. In India's history of public health, there has never been a plan with such minute documentation produced. In the past three decades, there has been a tremendous interest in researching the history of health in colonial India, both to analyze the role of "traditional" remedies in colonial and post-colonial India as well as the present ramifications of colonial medical interventions.

The Status of Health during the Colonial Regime in India

In general, it was believed that India's high mortality and high fertility rates ranged between 40 and 40 per 1000 people. The highest fatality rates occurred during famines and droughts. Famines were frequently followed by epidemics that exacerbated hunger problems. Famines had an impact on sanitation, water availability, and the ease with which diseases were disseminated, undermining the public health system. Malaria, smallpox, cholera, pulmonary TB, pneumonia, bronchitis, etc. were some of the common ailments that contributed to the high death rate, as did smallpox and, to a lesser extent, cholera. Malaria caused a 37 percent increase in the mortality rate throughout the colonial era. According to Amartya Sen, the government neglected half of the deaths brought on by famine and starvation. According to estimates, the epidemic caused 10 million fatalities in

Emerging Perspectives: Exploring Health in Post-Independence India

The colonial policy on modern medicine and the indigenous health system in postcolonial India must be considered when studying the history of the Indian healthcare system. Epidemics, leprosy,

malaria, mental health, health infrastructure, and health policies have all been the subject of numerous research. Numerous studies have examined various challenges relating to supply and access to healthcare in recent years. They give us insight into how public health neglect affects people negatively on an individual, family, and societal level. Studies that place a strong focus on the government's responsibility to provide public healthcare a number of commissions and committees were established to make recommendations on how to improve the efficiency and dependability of the public healthcare system.

Health Issues in Post-independence India

The Health Survey and Development Committee (Bhore Committee), Report of the Subcommittee on National Health (Sokhey Committee), Health Survey and Planning Committee, Chadha Committee, Mukerji Committee, and various other Committees' reports served as the foundation for the post-colonial Indian health system. The government was given the duty of providing preventative, primitive and curative health services. Health care services were available to everyone without exception and regardless of ability to pay, with the additional costs to be covered by public monies. By developing healthcare facilities with an equitable distribution in the rural areas, it was hoped to close the gap between the availability of healthcare in rural and urban areas. The government is required to provide the delivery mechanism and to supply the funding. This demonstrated a clear shift in the process of developing health policy in favor of the privatization of healthcare services. With public subsidies and low-cost financing, the private healthcare industry has expanded quickly as a result of this transition. The government's 1990s healthcare model reduced comprehensive primary healthcare to selective primary healthcare, limiting the scope of primary healthcare to only child and productive health, immunization, the control of specific diseases, and emergency services. The health seeker must use private healthcare providers for any remaining health issues. Public hospitals do exist and are accessible to everyone interested in using their services, but due to resource limitations, they have implemented a user-based filtering mechanism.

Conclusion

After the filing of the Reports of the Alma Ata Declaration and ICSSR & ICMR, this chapter begins by emphasizing the phrase "Health for all by 2000 AD" and the significance of primary healthcare (which showed large disparities and dissatisfaction with the existed healthcare system in the

entire world especially in developing and under-developing countries). These Reports suggested that every country create a national health policy. In actuality, 1983 saw the creation of India's first national health policy. During the Sixth Five Year Plan, the National Health Policy established objectives to achieve "Health for all by 2000 AD"; from that point on, all Plans and health-related programmes adhered to the NHP. As previously indicated, all doors were closed during the Sixth Five Year Plan. During the Eight Plan, the emphasis switched from "Health for All" to "Health for the Underprivileged," with full backing for privatization. The creation of competent health personnel cost two-thirds of all health expenditures under the Plan, yet it fell short of expectations. The decentralization of health planning and its execution was stressed under the Ninth Plan. The primary healthcare system had been operating below optimally, according to the Planning Committee and Expert Committee on Public Health. The Plan included programmes for at-risk populations like SC/ST, urban slum dwellers, hilly regions, women and children, etc. The Plan also had considerations for the health of the environment, the health of children, the cost of healthcare, and a favorable viewpoint for the second NHP.

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